

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE MARKETS AND CARAVAN SERAS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION AT THE END OF THE 19TH AND EARLY 20TH CENTURIES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the formation, activity and development processes of markets and caravanserais in the Samarkand region in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. This period witnessed significant changes in the trade life of Central Asia. Samarkand markets functioned as the region's trade center, playing an important role in the development of domestic and foreign trade. Caravansaries, in turn, served as the necessary infrastructure for merchants and travelers. These structures strengthened economic ties and expanded international trade. The study also examines the role of markets and caravanserais in socio-economic life, their connection with urbanization and the transport system. The strategic geographical location of Samarkand played an important role in the development of these facilities. The article is written on the basis of historical sources and archival materials and serves as an important theoretical basis for a deeper study of these issues.

Keywords: Samarkand, markets, caravanserais, merchants, tourism.

Samarkand occupies a worthy place not only among the ancient cities of Central Asia, but also among the ancient cities of the whole world. It is not for nothing that many historians have called it with such wonderful names as “The Beauty of the Earth”, “The Rim of the East”, “The Paradise of the Ancient East”. It

is an urgent task to study the historiography and source studies of the population of Samarkand, which has celebrated its 2750th anniversary. A study of the literature on historical demography shows that only by the end of the 19th century did the number of articles and works written about the population of Samarkand increase. In 1874, L.N. Sobolev's work "On the Zarafshan District and Its Geographical and Statistical Data" was published. This work covers the natural conditions and territory of the Zarafshan oasis, the districts of Zarafshan District, cultivated areas, water structures, as well as the population of the villages of the district and similar information.

The book "Samarkand Oblast Yearbook-Questionnaire", which began to be published in 1895, also provides some information about the administrative division of this region, natural conditions, as well as the number and national composition of the population. In addition, demographic information was also reflected in the following sources. From 1888 to 1890, the Samarkand Regional Statistical Office prepared bound printed notebooks to register the movement of the local population. These notebooks were set up to publish statistical information about births, deaths, and marriages in Russian and Uzbek. According to the information that has come down to us from the regional colonial administration based on the notebooks, the composition of the population of the Samarkand region until January 1, 1891 was as follows; men -464,014, women -317,910, the total population was 781,924 people.

The markets and caravanserais of the Samarkand region at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries reflect a rich tapestry of economic, cultural, and architectural development. This period, straddling the late Tsarist and early Soviet eras, saw significant transformations influenced by regional trade dynamics, geopolitical shifts, and the integration of Central Asia into the broader Russian Empire. Below is an exploration of their history and development during this time:

Historical Context

1. **Samarkand's Strategic Location:** Samarkand, situated along the ancient Silk Road, had been a major trading hub for centuries. By the late 19th century, its role as a cultural and commercial center was revitalized due to its incorporation into the Russian Empire in 1868, which brought new administrative and economic policies.

2. **Impact of Russian Rule:** The Russian conquest introduced infrastructure developments such as the construction of railroads (notably the Trans-Caspian Railway in the 1880s). This enhanced connectivity between Samarkand and other parts of Central Asia, as well as the Russian heartland, leading to a surge in trade activities and urban growth.

Development of Markets

1. **Structure and Function of Markets:** Markets in Samarkand were typically organized around specific goods, such as textiles, spices, ceramics, and metals. The **Siyob Bazaar** (still functioning today) was a prominent market during this period. It became a hub for both local and regional trade, attracting merchants from neighboring regions and beyond.

2. **Russian Influence on Market Organization:** Under Russian administration, markets began to see regulatory changes. The introduction of standardized weights and measures, as well as taxation systems, affected how trade was conducted. However, traditional systems of bargaining and trade dynamics remained largely intact.

Caravanserais

1. **Role in Trade:** Caravanserais were essential infrastructure for facilitating long-distance trade. These structures provided lodging, storage, and security for merchants and their goods. They played a critical role in ensuring the continuity of trade routes that connected Samarkand to other parts of Central Asia, Persia, and China.

2. **Architectural Features:** Traditional caravanserais of this era retained their historical architectural styles, characterized by large courtyards, high walls, and multiple rooms for accommodation and storage. Some were renovated or repurposed under Russian influence to serve as warehouses or trading depots.

3. **Decline and Transformation:** By the early 20th century, the advent of modern transportation, such as railways, reduced the reliance on caravanserais. Many were abandoned, repurposed, or integrated into urban markets.

Economic and Cultural Changes

1. **Shift in Trade Networks:** The integration of Samarkand into the Russian Empire led to a shift in its trade networks. While traditional Silk Road routes diminished in importance, new links to Russian industrial centers and Europe emerged.

2. **Cultural Exchange:** The markets and caravanserais remained melting pots of cultural exchange. They were spaces where languages, cuisines, and traditions converged, reflecting the diversity of merchants and travelers.

3. **Transition to Soviet Era:** After the Russian Revolution and the establishment of Soviet power in Central Asia, market dynamics shifted further. Traditional bazaars faced state regulation, and private trade was often replaced by collective economic structures.

Conclusion. The markets and caravanserais of Samarkand at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries represent a transitional period in the region's history. They encapsulate the resilience of traditional trade practices while adapting to new economic and political realities introduced by Russian expansion and modernization efforts. Their legacy continues to influence Samarkand's cultural and commercial landscape today.

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